

Simple and effective hybrid interpolation method for IC-GN² DVC algorithm

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Abstract: Digital volume correlation (DVC) method is widely used in three-dimensional strain field measurement of different materials. However, the common inverse compositional Gauss-Newton algorithm with the first-order shape function (IC-GN¹) cannot accurately and effectively measure the complex strain field. Although the inverse compositional Gauss-Newton algorithm with the second-order shape function (IC-GN²) can improve the calculation accuracy of the complex strain field, its low stability and calculation efficiency limit its used. The cubic spline interpolation and complex second-order shape function in the IC-GN iterative result in low calculation efficiency and poor system stability of IC-GN². In this work, a hybrid interpolation method is proposed. Firstly, cubic spline interpolation of deformed volume image is completed one time before DVC calculation to obtain the gray matrix of half-integer position. Then, the subvolume gray matrix of any position is obtained by simple linear interpolation in IC-GN² iterative calculation. At the same time, the second-order parameters in the second-order shape function matrix are normalized to improve the ill-condition of Hessian matrix. Finally, the subpixel displacement is obtained. The numerical simulation of rectangular and ring loading is used for verification. The DVC calculation results show that the IC-GN² based on hybrid interpolation maintains the high accuracy of the existing IC-GN², and improves the calculation stability. The calculation speed of the algorithm is increased by about two times, which is close to the speed of IC-GN¹.

Keywords: Digital volume correlation, Hybrid interpolation, IC-GN², Linear

1. Introduction

In the field of three-dimensional strain field measurement, DVC method has been widely used in material strain measurement based on CT scanning, such as bone deformation (Palanca, Cristofolini et al. 2016), nanoindentation (Patterson, Cordes et al. 2016), concrete cracking (Yang, Ren et al. 2017) and shear deformation of geotechnical materials (Li, Kong et al. 2020). Under simple deformation conditions, the existing DVC method has good accuracy and can effectively measure the internal three-dimensional strain field of different materials. However, in most cases, the material with complex internal structure may produce complex strain field under external load, which may have significant second-order deformation characteristics. DIC/DVC method with the first-order shape function appears to be inadequate, and there is a large error between the results and the actual strain (Wang and Pan 2019). Moreover, IC-GN² is widely used in DIC, especially in 3D-DIC for 3D reconstruction (Dana, Kevin et al. 2018), while the time-consuming IC-GN² severely limits the efficiency of real-time reconstruction.

In the conventional DIC/DVC analysis, the first-order shape function is generally used to describe the local deformation of the material, however the second-order shape function is needed to improve the calculation accuracy for the region with complex local strain (Lu and Cary 2000). Due to the complexity of the second-order form function method, it not only increases the calculation by nearly twice, but also it is more sensitive to the speckle quality, which is characterized by low system stability (Schreier and Sutton 2002, Wang and Pan 2015, Xu, Su et al. 2015, Yu and Pan 2015). In terms of computational efficiency, Gao et al. (Gao, Cheng et al. 2015) used the IC-GN² method based on the second-order shape function to construct the reversible Hessian matrix and improve the computational efficiency. Bai et al. (Bai, Jiang et al. 2017) constructed the equivalent second-order shape function matrix and improved the computational efficiency of the second-order shape function. Although the IC-GN² algorithm can accelerate the DIC method based on the second-order shape function, the IC-GN² algorithm used in the DVC method still has the problems of excessive calculation and poor stability. Therefore, Wang et al. (Wang and Pan 2019) used the adaptive lattice method to improve the calculation accuracy, and used different lattice sizes for different local strain regions to obtain higher calculation accuracy. Subsequently, Pan et al. (Pan and Zou 2020) adopted the quasi-Gauss point method to improve the calculation accuracy of complex deformation field. This method only uses the first-order shape function to avoid or significantly reduce the systematic error caused by the mismatch of shape function.

The above analysis are based on the local DVC method, and the strain field obtained by the global DVC method conforms to the deformation compatibility condition, which has good applicability for complex strain field. However, its calculation amount is larger than that of the local method. Therefore, Yang et al. (Yang and Bhattacharya 2019) adopted the mixed DVC method to improve its calculation efficiency. First, the local DVC method was used to obtain the initial value, and then the finite element method was used to improve the calculation accuracy. Subsequently, J. Yang et al. (Yang and Bhattacharya 2021) also uses adaptive lattice method for finite element mesh modeling to improve computational efficiency and accuracy.

However, the above methods have certain room for improvement in both computational stability and efficiency. For example, the adaptive lattice method and the global DVC method have the shortcomings of complex theory and difficult implementation. The computational efficiency of the global DVC method is generally low, and the local lattice cannot be too small in the case of poor speckle quality. The IC-GN² method based on second-order shape function has the advantages of simple principle and simple implementation, but it has the disadvantages of low computational stability and efficiency. In order to improve the shortcomings of IC-GN² algorithm, we deeply analyze the characteristics of second order function and IC-GN² algorithm, and try to optimize the key Hessian matrix calculation and subvoxel interpolation steps to improve the calculation accuracy and efficiency of IC-GN² algorithm based on second order function.

2. IC-GN algorithm

2.1 IC-GN¹

For the DIC/DVC method, IC-GN algorithm is almost a standard sub-pixel displacement iterative solution method. The typical IC-GN¹ algorithm flow based on the first-order shape function is shown in Fig. 1(a). This method only needs to solve the Hessian matrix once in the iterative calculation process, which greatly accelerates the solution of sub-pixel displacement. In the figure, $\mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1)$ is the first-order form function equation, where $f(\mathbf{x})$ and $g(\mathbf{x})$ are the gray intensity values at point $\mathbf{x}=(x,y,z)^T$ in the reference and target sub-volumes; $\xi=(\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z)^T$ is the local coordinates of integer voxel points in the reference sub-volume; $\mathbf{p}_1=(u, u_x, u_y, u_z, v, v_x, v_y, v_z, w, w_x, w_y, w_z)$ is the linear deformation vector; $\mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1)$ is the linear displacement mapping function used to describe the deformation of the target sub-volume; $\Delta \mathbf{p}_1$ is the incremental deformation vector; $\mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p}_1)$ is the incremental mapping function exerted on the reference sub-volume. The objective function of IC-GN algorithm is the ZNSSD function with good robustness, which can be expressed as (Eq.1) :

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the principle of the 3D IC-GN algorithm, (a) IC-GN¹, (b) IC-GN².

$$C_{ZNSSD}(\Delta \mathbf{p}_1) = \sum_{\xi} \left\{ \frac{f(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p}_1)) - f_m}{\sqrt{\sum_{\xi} [f(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p}_1)) - f_m]^2}} - \frac{g(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1)) - g_m}{\sqrt{\sum_{\xi} [g(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1)) - g_m]^2}} \right\}^2 \quad (1)$$

where f_m and g_m represent the mean intensity values of reference and deformed sub-volumes.

The first order function can be expressed as :

$$\mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1) = \begin{bmatrix} 1+u_x & u_y & u_z & u \\ v_x & 1+v_y & v_z & v \\ w_x & w_y & 1+w_z & w \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta x \\ \Delta y \\ \Delta z \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z \in [-M, M]$.

To solve $\Delta \mathbf{p}_1$, Eq.1 can be written as follows :

$$C_{ZSSD}(\Delta \mathbf{p}_1) = \sum_{\xi} \left\{ \frac{f(\mathbf{x}+\xi) + \nabla f \frac{\partial \mathbf{W}_1}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} \Delta \mathbf{p}_1 - f_m}{\sqrt{\sum_{\xi} [f(\mathbf{x}+\mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p}_1)) - f_m]^2}} - \frac{g(\mathbf{x}+\mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1)) - g_m}{\sqrt{\sum_{\xi} [g(\mathbf{x}+\mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1)) - g_m]^2}} \right\}^2 \quad (3)$$

where, $\nabla f = (f_x, f_y, f_z)$ is the gradient of the reference volume image in the x, y, z directions.

In order to get the minimum value of Eq.1, $\partial C_{ZSSD}(\Delta \mathbf{p}) / \partial(\Delta \mathbf{p}) = 0$, the solution can be obtained by least square method :

$$\Delta \mathbf{p}_1 = -\mathbf{H}_{12 \times 12}^{-1} \times \sum_{\xi} \left\{ \left(\nabla f \frac{\partial \mathbf{W}_1}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} \right)_{12 \times 1}^T \times \left[(f(\mathbf{x}+\xi) - f_m) - \frac{\Delta f}{\Delta g} (g(\mathbf{x}+\mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1)) - g_m) \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

The Hessian matrix can be written as:

$$\mathbf{H}_{12 \times 12} = \sum_{\xi} \left\{ \left(\nabla f \frac{\partial \mathbf{W}_1}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} \right)_{12 \times 1}^T \times \left(\nabla f \frac{\partial \mathbf{W}_1}{\partial \mathbf{p}_1} \right)_{1 \times 12} \right\} \quad (5)$$

The updated iterative formulas of the shape function $\mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1)$:

$$\mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1) \leftarrow \mathbf{W}_1(\mathbf{W}_1^{-1}(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1), \mathbf{p}_1) = \mathbf{W}_1(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1) \mathbf{W}_1^{-1}(\xi; \mathbf{p}_1) \quad (6)$$

In the DVC calculation process, the general reliability-oriented strategy is used to estimate the initial value (Pan, Wang et al. 2014), and the interpolation coefficient table of the deformed volume image is completed once before the actual calculation, and then the accurate subvoxel displacement is obtained by IC-GN¹ algorithm on the basis of the initial displacement. In the general IC-GN iterative calculation process, interpolation calculation is an indispensable step. Although curve fitting algorithm (Pan, Xu et al. 2005) or pre-interpolation method (Li and Shu 2020) can be used to avoid time-consuming interpolation calculation in some simple or small deformation cases, it is difficult to meet the requirements for large deformation cases. And for the complex deformation conditions, the accuracy of the IC-GN¹ algorithm is also difficult to achieve high-precision analysis requirements (Lu and Cary 2000).

2.2 IC-GN²

Since the IC-GN¹ algorithm cannot meet the high-precision calculation of complex deformation field, many scholars introduce the second-order shape function to describe the local deformation state. Compared with IC-GN¹ algorithm, the accuracy of IC-GN² algorithm based on second-order shape function has been greatly improved, and the algorithm of this method has been gradually developed (Lu and Cary 2000, Gao, Cheng et al. 2015, Bai, Jiang et al. 2017). The calculation steps of typical IC-GN² algorithm are shown in Fig. 1(b).

The general second-order function can be expressed as :

$$\mathbf{W}_2(\xi; \mathbf{p}_2) = \begin{bmatrix} 0.5u_{xx} & u_{xy} & 0.5u_{yy} & u_{yz} & 0.5u_{zz} & u_{zx} & 1+u_x & u_y & u_z & u \\ 0.5v_{xx} & v_{xy} & 0.5v_{yy} & v_{yz} & 0.5v_{zz} & v_{zx} & v_x & 1+v_y & v_z & v \\ 0.5w_{xx} & w_{xy} & 0.5w_{yy} & w_{yz} & 0.5w_{zz} & w_{zx} & w_x & w_y & 1+w_z & w \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x^2 & xy & y^2 & yz & z^2 & zx & x & y & z & 1 \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_2$ is:

$$\mathbf{p}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} u, u_x, u_y, u_z, u_{xx}, u_{xy}, u_{yy}, u_{yz}, u_{zz}, u_{zx}, \\ v, v_x, v_y, v_z, v_{xx}, v_{xy}, v_{yy}, v_{yz}, v_{zz}, v_{zx}, \\ w, w_x, w_y, w_z, w_{xx}, w_{xy}, w_{yy}, w_{yz}, w_{zz}, w_{zx} \end{pmatrix}^T \quad (8)$$

However, according to the inversion conditions of the Hessian matrix, it can be seen that the matrix inversion cannot be solved in the form of Eq.(7). Therefore, it is necessary to add six to Eq.(7) to meet the invertibility of the matrix (Gao, Cheng et al. 2015). The corresponding parameters of the second-order shape function matrix are shown in appendix A.

$$\begin{cases} x'^2 = (1+s_1)x^2 + s_2xy + s_3y^2 + s_4yz + s_5z^2 + s_6zx + s_7x + s_8y + s_9z + s_{10} + o(h^2) \\ x'y' = s_{11}x^2 + (1+s_{12})xy + s_{13}y^2 + s_{14}yz + s_{15}z^2 + s_{16}zx + s_{17}x + s_{18}y + s_{19}z + s_{20} + o(h^2) \\ y'^2 = s_{21}x^2 + s_{22}xy + (1+s_{23})y^2 + s_{24}yz + s_{25}z^2 + s_{26}zx + s_{27}x + s_{28}y + s_{29}z + s_{30} + o(h^2) \\ y'z' = s_{31}x^2 + s_{32}xy + s_{33}y^2 + (1+s_{34})yz + s_{35}z^2 + s_{36}zx + s_{37}x + s_{38}y + s_{39}z + s_{40} + o(h^2) \\ z'^2 = s_{41}x^2 + s_{42}xy + s_{43}y^2 + s_{44}yz + (1+s_{45})z^2 + s_{46}zx + s_{47}x + s_{48}y + s_{49}z + s_{50} + o(h^2) \\ z'x' = s_{51}x^2 + s_{52}xy + s_{53}y^2 + s_{54}yz + s_{55}z^2 + (1+s_{56})zx + s_{57}x + s_{58}y + s_{59}z + s_{60} + o(h^2) \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The corresponding shape functions are rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{W}_2(\xi; \mathbf{p}_2) = [x'^2, x'y', y'^2, y'z', z'^2, z'x', x', y', z', 1]^T$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1+s_1 & s_2 & s_3 & s_4 & s_5 & s_6 & s_7 & s_8 & s_9 & s_{10} \\ s_{11} & 1+s_{12} & s_{13} & s_{14} & s_{15} & s_{16} & s_{17} & s_{18} & s_{19} & s_{20} \\ s_{21} & s_{22} & 1+s_{23} & s_{24} & s_{25} & s_{26} & s_{27} & s_{28} & s_{29} & s_{30} \\ s_{31} & s_{32} & s_{33} & 1+s_{34} & s_{35} & s_{36} & s_{37} & s_{38} & s_{39} & s_{40} \\ s_{41} & s_{42} & s_{43} & s_{44} & 1+s_{45} & s_{46} & s_{47} & s_{48} & s_{49} & s_{50} \\ s_{51} & s_{52} & s_{53} & s_{54} & s_{55} & 1+s_{56} & s_{57} & s_{58} & s_{59} & s_{60} \\ 0.5u_{xx} & u_{xy} & 0.5u_{yy} & u_{yz} & 0.5u_{zz} & u_{zx} & 1+u_x & u_y & u_z & u \\ 0.5v_{xx} & v_{xy} & 0.5v_{yy} & v_{yz} & 0.5v_{zz} & v_{zx} & v_x & 1+v_y & v_z & v \\ 0.5w_{xx} & w_{xy} & 0.5w_{yy} & w_{yz} & 0.5w_{zz} & w_{zx} & w_x & w_y & 1+w_z & w \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x^2 \\ xy \\ y^2 \\ yz \\ z^2 \\ zx \\ x \\ y \\ z \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

The other calculation steps are similar to IC-GN¹ algorithm, and finally the displacement field of complex strain can be calculated. However, according to the Eq.(10), it can be seen that due to the second-order shape function involves the second-order gradient in the deformed volume image and the complex Hessian matrix solution, the IC-GN² algorithm has low stability and low computational efficiency(Gao, Cheng et al. 2015, Wang and Pan 2019).

2.3 The hybrid interpolation method

According to the analysis of the first two sections, we can temporarily summarize:

(1) For complex deformation, whether IC-GN¹ or IC-GN² algorithm, subvoxel interpolation is an indispensable step in the iterative process of IC-GN algorithm. In the usual IC-GN calculation process, we usually use cubic spline interpolation method to obtain subvoxel gray value matrix. Although the cubic spline interpolation method can obtain high accuracy, it is time-consuming. As shown in Table 1. (Pan, Wang et al. 2014), without considering

matrix acceleration, the computation of subvoxel interpolation is at least 2-3 times more than that of Hessian matrix, and the interpolation computation is also related to the number of iterations. The greater the number of iterations of IC-GN, the greater the amount of interpolation computation and the greater the gap between them. Secondly, the matrix-related calculation can be well vectorized to optimize and improve the calculation efficiency from the software and hardware levels, so as to reduce the time-consuming related to matrix calculation. However, the interpolation calculation is difficult to be simply converted into vector form for acceleration, which eventually leads to the interpolation calculation amount much larger than that of matrix correlation such as Hessian. Therefore, under the premise of ensuring the accuracy, the computational efficiency related to interpolation calculation must be improved, especially for IC-GN².

Table 1 The arithmetic operations number of DVC method (Pan, Wang et al. 2014)

Arithmetic operation	Addition/subtraction operations	Multiplications/division
Computation of Hessian matrix	$25M^3$	$180 M^3$
Subvoxel interpolation	$84IM^3$	$207 IM^3$
Total number	$25M^3 + 84IM^3$	$180M^3 + 207IM^3$

The pre-interpolation method (Li and Shu 2020) can effectively improve the computational efficiency under small strain conditions. The method uses cubic spline interpolation to obtain the gray value matrix of half integer position at once, and then it is used to extract subvoxel in curve fitting method or IC-GN¹ algorithm iterative calculation, which completely avoids subvoxel interpolation calculation. However, this method is not accurate enough under complex deformation conditions, and high precision cubic spline interpolation is very time consuming. Therefore, inspired by this method, on the basis of the half-integer pre-interpolation method, we add linear interpolation in the iterative calculation process of IC-GN² to improve the accuracy of sub-pixel interpolation. We call this method is hybrid interpolation method.

The simple schematic diagram of the mixed interpolation method is shown in Fig. 2. First, the gray value of half-integer is calculated by cubic spline interpolation. Then, the subvoxel gray value at any point is obtained by linear interpolation. It can be seen from Fig. 2 that the cubic spline interpolation can obtain the best accuracy, while the ordinary linear interpolation accuracy is insufficient, and the hybrid interpolation method improves the interpolation accuracy, while it is still lower than the cubic spline interpolation method. Although the accuracy of the hybrid interpolation method is poor, it does not affect its application in IC-GN algorithm. The calculation steps of the mixed interpolation method in the deformed volume image are shown in Fig. 3. In each IC-GN iterative calculation process, only the linear interpolation is carried out on the basis of the half-integer cubic spline interpolation, which greatly accelerates the computational efficiency of the subvoxel interpolation in theory.

Figure 2. The illustration of the hybrid interpolation, (a) the interpolation curves of different interpolation methods, (b) the absolute error curves of different interpolation methods.

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of the implementation of hybrid interpolation: (a) local interpolation unit comprised of $4 \times 4 \times 4$ voxels; (b) interpolation block surrounded by 8 integer voxel points (green) and 19 half-integer voxel points (blue), and the subvoxel location by linear-interpolation

The linear interpolation formula in the subvoxel position is:

$$g(x, y, z) = \sum_{l=0}^1 \sum_{m=0}^1 \sum_{n=0}^1 a_{lmn} \Delta x^l \Delta y^m \Delta z^n \quad (12)$$

where, a_{lmn} is a linear interpolation coefficient, Δx , Δy , Δz are offsets in local coordinates.

In the conventional IC-GN algorithm, the gradients of the intensity within the reference sub-volume $\nabla f(f_x, f_y, f_z)$ are gradients under integer voxel conditions. Since the deformed volume image matrix is interpolated, the differential formula needs to be corrected as:

$$\nabla f = \left(\frac{\partial f(\mathbf{x} + \xi)}{\partial x} \quad \frac{\partial f(\mathbf{y} + \xi)}{\partial y} \quad \frac{\partial f(\mathbf{z} + \xi)}{\partial z} \right) / 2 \quad (13)$$

Due to the half-integer pre-interpolation calculation, the memory occupancy of the deformed volume image is increased by 8 times, and the corresponding gradient matrix is also increased by 8 times. Therefore, in order to

reduce the memory occupancy of the hybrid interpolation method, the block method is used to alleviate the problem of excessive memory occupancy(Li and Shu 2020).

(2) Second order function matrix optimization

According to the Eq.(7), the left part of the second-order shape function is a matrix of 10×10 , which increases by 6.25 times compared with the 4×4 of the first-order shape function, and accordingly increases the difficulty of solving Hessian matrix and inverse calculation. At the same time, because the second-order shape function needs the second-order gradient of the reference volume image, the system stability of the second-order IC-GN² algorithm is lower (Lan, Gao et al. 2021).

Further analysis shows that the offsets of x, y, z of the first-order shape function are between $[-M, M]$, while the values of $x^2, xy, y^2, yz, z^2, zx, x, y, z, 1$ of the second-order shape function are between $[-M^2, M^2]$, and the difference between them is a rate M . According to Eq.(5), the test calculation results show that the Hessian matrix of the second-order shape function is significantly ill-conditioned, and the difference on the diagonal of the Hessian matrix will increase with the increase of M , which eventually leads to the low stability of the second-order IC-GN² algorithm. Therefore, in order to reduce the ill-posedness of Hessian matrix and improve the stability of the second-order IC-GN² algorithm, we improve the right side of the second-order shape Eq.(10):

$$[x^2, xy, y^2, yz, z^2, zx, x, y, z, 1]^T \rightarrow [x^2/M, xy/M, y^2/M, yz/M, z^2/M, zx/M, x, y, z, 1]^T \quad (14)$$

Eq.(14) normalizes all the parameters of each shape function to the same order of magnitude. At the same time, the corresponding parameters on the left side of the second-order shape Eq.(10) should also be corrected by M . The modified second-order shape function can slow down the ill-posedness of the Hessian matrix, and theoretically improve the system stability of the second-order IC-GN² algorithm.

3. Experimental verification using numerical tests

3.1 numerical tests of trigonometric displacement(sample 1)

In order to verify the accuracy and effectiveness of the hybrid interpolation method in the second-order IC-GN² algorithm, we carried out the numerical simulation test of complex small deformation. In this work, a $100 \times 100 \times 2000$ voxel size referencing a 3D speckle pattern ($R=4$ voxels, $s=120,000$) was first generated, as shown in the inset of figure 4. Then, according to the Fourier shift theorem, a trigonometric function displacement field is generated in the z -axis direction as shown in Eq.(15), where $T=1.2 \times 10^5$, $b=1,3,5$, and the unit is voxel. All DVC analyses were calculated by an in-home DVC software iDVC (<https://github.com/lichengshengHK/iDVC>), and the desktop computer is i7-6700 CPU 3.40 GHz, 32 GB RAM. The lattice of DVC calculation window is $41 \times 41 \times 41$, and a

$$z' - z = w(z) = b \sin\left(\frac{z^2}{T}\right), T = 1.2 \times 10^5, b = 1, 3, 5 \quad (15)$$

Figure 4. The illustration of z-axis displacement field loading diagram of cuboid block

We compared the calculation results of different methods in the displacement field. Before the analysis, we first agreed on the abbreviation of different methods:

- 1) IC-GN²-2n represents the half-integer pre-interpolation method of IC-GN² algorithm.
- 2) IC-GN²-2nL represents IC-GN² algorithm based on hybrid interpolation method.

Fig. 5 shows the displacement field results and error curves of IC-GN¹, IC-GN², IC-GN²-2n and IC-GN²-2nL algorithm with different b values. It can be seen from the figure that regardless of the value of b , the accuracy of IC-GN¹ algorithm is the worst, especially the error increases gradually with the increase of the strain, and the error value is far greater than that of other methods. For the IC-GN²-2n pre-interpolation method, although the error of this method is smaller than that of IC-GN¹ algorithm, its stability is very poor, and there is a strong sawtooth fluctuation. Although its stability is alleviated with the increase of b value, it is almost unable to meet the requirements of high-precision analysis. Compared with IC-GN¹ algorithm, the results of IC-GN² algorithm show that the accuracy is significantly improved, and the numerical error of displacement is significantly reduced. Although it has certain volatility in a small range, the overall stability is good. Finally, we compare the calculation results of IC-GN²-2nL algorithm. It can be seen that the error of IC-GN²-2nL algorithm is similar to that of IC-GN² algorithm, even in some positions, and the peak value of displacement error is smaller than that of IC-GN² algorithm.

Figure 5. The displacement (u_z) obtained using four different DVC methods (IC-GN¹, IC-GN², IC-GN²-2n and IC-GN²-2nL).

(a) z displacement curves and (b) error of z displacement curves of $b = 1$, (c) z displacement curves and (b) error of z displacement curves of $b = 3$, (e) z displacement curves and (b) error of z displacement curves of $b = 5$.

Fig.6 shows the strain field comparison results calculated by different methods. First of all, we can find that the strain results calculated by IC-GN²-2n are the worst. The strain calculated by this method has significant volatility, and the strain error is significantly higher than that by other methods. IC-GN¹ algorithm has good accuracy in the case of small strain, but with the increase of strain, its accuracy has decreased significantly, and also has significant fluctuation characteristics. In contrast, the results of IC-GN² and IC-GN²-2nL show that the strain error is significantly reduced, and the strain error curves of IC-GN²-2nL have significant similarity at $b = 1$, although IC-GN²-2nL has slight fluctuation characteristics. When $b = 3, 5$, in the small strain range, the strain errors of IC-GN² and IC-GN²-2nL fluctuate in a similar range. However, with the increase of strain, near the strain error peak of IC-

GN², IC-GN²-2nL shows good stability, and the strain error is reduced by 50 ~ 60 %. In other words, IC-GN²-2nL has better accuracy and system stability, especially for the calculation of large and complex strain field.

Figure 6. The strain (e_{zz}) obtained using four different DVC methods (IC-GN¹, IC-GN², IC-GN²-2n and IC-GN²-2nL). (a) strain curves and (b) error of strain curves of $b = 1$, (c) strain curves and (d) error of strain curves of $b = 3$, (e) strain curves and (f) error of strain curves of $b = 5$.

3.2 Computational efficiency of the proposed DVC method

In summary, the comparison of the analysis results of the two groups of numerical simulation experiments shows that the proposed hybrid interpolation method can not only slightly improve the accuracy of the IC-GN² algorithm, but also effectively improve its stability. The hybrid interpolation method has the advantages of simple principle and easy programming. On the basis of the original IC-GN² algorithm, only a small improvement is made

to achieve better accuracy. However, when discussing the precision of the hybrid interpolation method, the computational efficiency is also our concern. Table 2 shows the computational efficiency comparison results of the two groups of numerical simulations. We use IC-GN¹ as the comparison benchmark. It can be seen that the calculation speed of traditional IC-GN² is almost half of that of IC-GN¹, and the calculation speed of IC-GN²-2nL is similar to that of IC-GN¹, that is to say, the calculation speed of IC-GN²-2nL is about twice that of traditional IC-GN². In summary, although the IC-GN²-2nL algorithm increases the memory requirement, the time-consuming cubic spline interpolation only needs to be calculated once. Therefore, the time-consuming cubic spline interpolation calculation is completely avoided in the IC-GN iterative calculation process. Instead, the simple linear interpolation is performed on the basis of half-integer pre-interpolation, which greatly improves the computational efficiency of IC-GN² algorithm and improves the system stability.

Table 2 The calculate speed and speed-up ratio of different DVC methods

Example name		IC-GN ¹		IC-GN ²		IC-GN ² -2nL	
		Speed [POI/s]	Speed-up ratio	Speed [POI/s]	Speed-up ratio	Speed [POI/s]	Speed-up ratio
Sample1 (41×41×41)	$b=1$	186.3	1	106.2	0.57	195.6	1.05
	$b=3$	185.7	1	105.8	0.57	195.0	1.05
	$b=5$	182.4	1	102.0	0.56	189.7	1.04

4. Discussion and Conclusions

In this work, we propose a simple and efficient hybrid interpolation method for IC-GN² algorithm based on second-order shape function. The improved IC-GN²-2nL algorithm has better accuracy than the traditional IC-GN², and has better stability. The calculation speed is nearly doubled, and the calculation efficiency of IC-GN¹ is achieved. The IC-GN²-2nL method based on hybrid interpolation only needs one half integer cubic spline interpolation calculation, then only needs simple linear interpolation calculation in the iterative process of IC-GN, which greatly improves the computational efficiency. At the same time, the second-order shape function matrix is improved, which improves the ill-condition of Hessian matrix and the stability of IC-GN² algorithm. In complex three-dimensional strain field measurement, IC-GN²-2nL method based on hybrid interpolation method is expected to become an efficient three-dimensional strain field measurement method.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that there are no competing financial interests or personal relationships to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A: the parameters of p_2

Ther related parameters of the second-order shape function matrix:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} s_1 = uu_{xx} + (1+u_x)^2 - 1 \\ s_2 = 2(uu_{xy} + (1+u_x)u_y) \\ s_3 = uu_{yy} + u_y^2 \\ s_4 = 2(uu_{yz} + u_y u_z) \\ s_5 = uu_{zz} + u_z^2 \end{array} \right. , \left\{ \begin{array}{l} s_6 = 2(uu_{zx} + u_z(1+u_x)) \\ s_7 = 2u(1+u_x) \\ s_8 = 2uu_y \\ s_9 = 2uu_z \\ s_{10} = u^2 \end{array} \right. \quad (16)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} s_{11} = 0.5(uv_{xx} + vu_{xx}) + (1+u_x)v_x \\ s_{12} = uv_{xy} + vu_{xy} + (1+u_x)(1+v_y) + v_x u_y - 1 \\ s_{13} = 0.5(uv_{yy} + vu_{yy}) + u_y(1+v_y) \\ s_{14} = uv_{yz} + vu_{yz} + u_y v_z + (1+v_y)u_z \\ s_{15} = 0.5(uv_{zz} + vu_{zz}) + u_z v_z \end{array} \right. , \left\{ \begin{array}{l} s_{16} = uv_{zx} + vu_{zx} + u_z v_x + v_z(1+u_x) \\ s_{17} = uv_x + v(1+u_x) \\ s_{18} = u(1+v_y) + vu_y \\ s_{19} = uv_z + vu_z \\ s_{20} = uv \end{array} \right. \quad (17)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} s_{21} = vv_{xx} + v_x^2 \\ s_{22} = 2(vv_{xy} + (1+v_y)u_x) \\ s_{23} = vv_{yy} + (1+v_y)^2 - 1 \\ s_{24} = 2(vv_{yz} + (1+v_y)v_z) \\ s_{25} = vv_{zz} + v_z^2 \end{array} \right. , \left\{ \begin{array}{l} s_{26} = 2(vv_{zx} + v_z v_x) \\ s_{27} = 2vv_x \\ s_{28} = 2v(1+v_y) \\ s_{29} = 2vv_z \\ s_{30} = v^2 \end{array} \right. \quad (18)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} s_{31} = 0.5(vw_{xx} + wv_{xx}) + v_x wv_x \\ s_{32} = vw_{xy} + wv_{xy} + v_x w_y + w_x(1+v_y) \\ s_{33} = 0.5(vw_{yy} + wv_{yy}) + w_y(1+v_y) \\ s_{34} = vw_{yz} + wv_{yz} + (1+v_y)(1+w_z) + w_y v_z - 1 \\ s_{35} = 0.5(vw_{zz} + wv_{zz}) + v_z(1+w_z) \end{array} \right. , \left\{ \begin{array}{l} s_{36} = vw_{zx} + wv_{zx} + v_z w_x + v_x(1+w_z) \\ s_{37} = vw_x + wv_x \\ s_{38} = vw_y + w(1+v_y) \\ s_{39} = v(1+w_z) + wv_z \\ s_{40} = vw \end{array} \right. \quad (19)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} s_{41} = ww_{xx} + w_x^2 \\ s_{42} = 2(ww_{xy} + w_x w_y) \\ s_{43} = ww_{yy} + w_y^2 \\ s_{44} = 2(ww_{yz} + w_y(1+w_z)) \\ s_{45} = ww_{zz} + (1+w_z)^2 - 1 \end{array} \right. , \left\{ \begin{array}{l} s_{46} = 2(ww_{zx} + w_x(1+w_z)) \\ s_{47} = 2ww_x \\ s_{48} = 2ww_y \\ s_{49} = 2w(1+w_z) \\ s_{50} = w^2 \end{array} \right. \quad (20)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} s_{51} = 0.5(wu_{xx} + uw_{xx}) + w_x(1+u_x) \\ s_{52} = wu_{xy} + uw_{xy} + w_x u_y + w_y(1+u_x) \\ s_{53} = 0.5(wu_{yy} + uw_{yy}) + w_y u_y \\ s_{54} = wu_{yz} + uw_{yz} + w_y u_z + u_y(1+w_z) \\ s_{55} = 0.5(wu_{zz} + uw_{zz}) + u_z(1+w_z) \end{array} \right. , \left\{ \begin{array}{l} s_{56} = wu_{zx} + uw_{zx} + (1+w_z)(1+u_x) + u_z w_x - 1 \\ s_{57} = w(1+u_x) + uw_x \\ s_{58} = wu_y + uw_y \\ s_{59} = wu_z + u(1+w_z) \\ s_{60} = wu \end{array} \right. \quad (21)$$

Appendix B: the result of the proposed method for IC-GN1

In order to verify the effectiveness of the hybrid interpolation method in IC-GN¹, we compared the numerical simulation results of IC-GN¹ and IC-GN¹-2nL. We refer to the numerical simulation example in Ref. (Li and Shu 2020). Fig. 7 shows the mean bias error and standard deviation error curves under different window lattices. It can be seen that the mean bias error of IC-GN¹-2nL based on hybrid interpolation method is similar to that of IC-GN¹, and keeps in the same range, while its fluctuation period is about half of that of traditional IC-GN¹. The standard deviation curves of IC-GN¹-2nL remained below 0.00075voxel on the whole. Although it was larger than that of IC-GN¹, it had reached the requirement of high precision analysis.

Figure 7 Mean bias error and standard deviation error curves of different IC-GN¹ methods.

As can be seen from Fig.7, the hybrid interpolation method proposed in this paper is also suitable for IC-GN¹ algorithm. Due to the reduction of time-consuming cubic spline interpolation calculation, simple linear interpolation calculation improves the speed nearly doubles times. That is to say, the hybrid interpolation method recommended in this paper is suitable for IC-GN¹ and IC-GN², which can improve the actuarial efficiency of DVC method as a whole, and can effectively promote the application of DVC method in three-dimensional strain field measurement of various materials.

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